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MINEARC WEBINAR Mineral resource and sustainable exploration 23–24 April 2024 Abstracts

Shenghong Yang, Nils Jansson, and Juha Kaija eds.

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Machine learning topic detection of social media attitudes about mineral development in Europe

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For reasons of both energy security and the green energy transition, the European Union has recently sponsored several initiatives that seek to understand and characterize the mineral resources of member states in order to prepare for independence in green energy development. Currently, Europe imports the vast majority of its critical minerals, including 85% of its niobium from Brazil, 93% magnesium from China, and 98% borate from Turkey (van Wieringen and Álvarez, 2022). Rare earth minerals are a particular risk-point for the EU's plans for green energy development, as the market is currently dominated by countries with a tenuous relationship with the west.

Within this context of necessity for reliably and sustainably sourced critical minerals, attitudes within Europe about mining and exploration vary widely and are sometimes contentious. Europe has some of the most robust environmental and social regulations in the world, and stakeholder opinions and attitudes are an extremely important check point on the road to critical mineral development. One significant example of the power of public opinion is the 2022 revocation of Rio Tinto's permit to mine Lithium in Serbia due to mass protests over environmental concerns. According to Reuters, this \$2.4 billion project could supply up 90% of Europe's current lithium needs, if completed (Sekularac, 2022). This example highlights the importance of stakeholder opinion in decision-making around critical mineral exploration, characterization, and development.

One of the major difficulties in addressing stakeholder concerns is the fact that no population is monolithic in its opinion, and different sets of stakeholders have different and often competing priorities and values. To understand and address stakeholder concerns, it is necessary to identify not only what stakeholders are saying about a given project or industry, but also which stakeholders are saying it, how much they are saying it, which stakeholders disagree, and how much they disagree. To that end, the author uses a machine learning technique called latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) to statistically identify topics of concern to stakeholders based on their stated opinions. These opinions may be stated within the context of an interview, written in a blog or news article, or posted on social media. In this presentation, results are presented from a study of social media opinions in four EU member states, including the Czech Republic, Portugal, Poland, and Finland. The LDA method is language agnostic, which allows for analysis to be performed on social media posted in the native language of the focal country and compared across the set. The concerns, issues, and topics detected from this analysis vary widely across the target countries, and range from resource nationalism to environmental concerns, to EU policy criticisms, to discussions of the green transition and future prospects of space mining. Understanding these topics and the stakeholder values they represent is crucial to determining EU mineral and industrial development going forward.

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